

Kinematic Fields Measurement during Orthogonal Cutting : New High-Speed Imaging System and Experimental set-up.

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Abstract: Application of the Digital Image Correlation technique for kinematic fields measurement during orthogonal cutting allows to identify localized deformation band. However, ensuring a random speckle pattern in the sub-millimetric region of interest is crucial. In this paper, light issues are discussed. Optical solutions to enhance the light intensity within a sub-millimetric region of interest are given. According to the size of this region, a dedicated high-speed imaging system is proposed. Identification of the optical parameters function of the cutting conditions is discussed. The experimental set-up is presented and first orthogonal cutting tests are conducted for validation. Finally, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique is applied to measure the kinematic fields during one segment chip formation.

Keywords : light, high-speed imaging system, optical parameters, DIC, kinematic fields.

1 Introduction

Accurate relevant data of kinematic fields during orthogonal cutting are with great importance to have an insight on the mechanisms of chip formation. It enables to validate or to enhance material behaviour laws that could better describe the thermo-mechanical load at local scale. In this context, orthogonal cutting tests were conducted to enable direct measurements of the kinematics fields in the cutting zone. During the cutting process, the material is subjected to high strain (>1) with a strain rate up to 10^3 s^{-1} . Understanding the mechanisms of chip formation under complex thermomechanical loads remain one of the scientifically challenging tasks regarding the size of the region of interest ($<1 \text{ mm}^2$).

Quik-Stop Devices (QSD) has been first employed to study the mechanism of chip formation (Brown, 1976; Vorm, 1976). An alternative method allowing *in-situ* visualization of chip formation is the use of high-speed cameras. Micro-scale grid printing was one of the

useful techniques for surface preparation that enable particle tracking for kinematic fields measurement (Bitans, 1965; Childs, 1971; Jeelani, 1982a, b; Ghadbeigi, 2008; Pujana, 2008). Instead of using a printed micro-scale grid, (List, 2013) employed the mechanical scratching method to draw flow lines parallel to the cutting direction. The kinematics fields were determined by the streamline models (Hasani, 2008; Bi, 2009). Recently, on polished and etched Ti-6Al-4V workpiece, (Pottier, 2014) used the DIC technique to return the incremental displacements fields. Loss in image quality was behind the choice of the incremental correlation. Using the 7d software with the local Digital Image Correlation approach (Vacher, 1999), a Zero-Mean Normalized Cross-Correlation (ZMNCC) criteria (Pan, 2009) was chosen to overcome light fluctuation issues. In fact, the ZMNCC criteria is insensitive to both offset and linear scale in lighting. Through the developed finite element framework, post-processing of the incremental displacements data enables particle tracking. Based on the work of (Whitenton, 2010) and (Pottier, 2014), (Harzallah, 2018) developed a new optical system allowing for coupled kinematic and thermal fields measurements. Instrumented orthogonal cutting tests were conducted on Ti-6Al-4V. The obtained experimental data were used to validate a new material behaviour law (Harzallah, 2016, 2017).

The highly interest in understanding local phenomena during chip formation has led researchers to develop a dedicated experimental protocol allowing for *in-situ* measurement of the kinematic fields (Meurer, 2020; Thimm, 2021; Yang, 2021; Zhang, 2021). The obtained data can then be used for inverse identification of material behaviour law parameters (Thimm, 2019) implemented for numerical simulation of orthogonal cutting.

Nowadays, the use of the DIC technique for kinematic field measurement is widely increasing. For more details, the lecturer can refer to (Vacher, 1999; Hild, 2006; Fazzini, 2009; Pan, 2009; Pottier, 2010). It allows to measure a full-field displacement with sub-pixel accuracy and to estimate the full-field strain. However, surface preparation and the speckle resistance under high thermomechanical loads may induce difficulties in applying the DIC technique. In this paper, light issues encountered in the context of kinematic fields measurement during orthogonal cutting are discussed and optical solution are proposed. With respect to the sub-millimetric size of the region of interest, a dedicated high-speed imaging system is proposed. Identification of the optical parameters function of the cutting conditions is discussed. Finally, first orthogonal cutting tests are conducted for validation.

2 Experimental approach

2.1 Light issues

Lighting a sub-millimetric region undergone high deformation, crack initiation and growth, and off-plane motion is crucial. Figure 1 and 2 give concepts related to light issues encountered in the context of kinematic fields' measurement during orthogonal cutting. Due to non-uniformity in light distribution (Figure 1.a and b), decrease in light intensity with the radius R will lead to the appearance of areas underexposed to light. Optical solution that ensures uniformity in the light intensity distributions (Figure 1.c) can reduce the risk of appearance of areas underexposed to light. (Figure 2) describes the impact of surface flatness on the image quality using exterior and coaxial collimated light. With exterior light (Figure 2.a), the light beams which have not returned to the

optical channel will stimulate the appearance of black spots on the image. The last will be less pronounced when using coaxial collimated light (Figure 2.b).

Figure 1: Light intensity distributions: a) external light; b) coaxial scattered light and c) coaxial collimated light.

Figure 2: Impact of the surface flatness using: a) external light and b) coaxial collimated light.

2.2 Proposed optical solution

To ensure uniformity in light intensity distribution, collimated light beam is recommended. For coaxial collimated lighting, a plano-convex lens can be mounted in a cage system (figure 3) and coupled with a beam-splitter (figure 5.b). In the case of external lighting, the plano-convex lens can be mounted in a collimation tube. To obtain maximum light intensity, focalised light beam (figure 4) obtained by mean of two plano-convex lens can be used.

Figure 3: proposed optical solution for coaxial collimated lighting: a) exploded view and b) volumetric cut and light beam path.

Figure 4: proposed optical solution for external lighting with focalised light beam: a) details of the focus; and b) focalised light beam (image from Thorlabs).

2.3 Optical system for high-speed imaging

Under the spatial resolution of 512×512 pixels, an X15 magnification lens leads to obtain an acceptable scene size for kinematic field's measurement during one segment chip formation with feed equal to 0,25mm. An infinity-corrected X15 magnification lens was chosen allowing for a maximum transmission in the visible spectrum range (up to 96%). In addition, it ensures nearly secure working distance which is equal to 23,8mm. Using an infinity-corrected lens imposes the use of tube lens. A 200mm focal length tube lens was chosen in order to keep the magnification at X15. The main advantage of choosing an infinity-corrected lens is that it enables introducing beam-splitter for coaxial illumination (figure 10.b) and edgepass filter to reduce noise induced by thermal waves (Pan, 2011) in the so called infinity space delimited by the lens and the tube lens. Moreover, By mean of only changing the tube lens (400mm focal length), magnification will be multiplied by X2 leading to X30 magnification without changing the working distance.

Figure 5: design of the optical system: a) without coaxial illumination and b) with coaxial illumination.

2.4 Experimental set-up

Ti-6Al-4V rectangular workpiece with a width of cut equal to 3mm was polished and etched. The orthogonal cutting test is conducted with a cutting speed of 3m/min and a feed of 0,2mm. Uncoated carbide cutting inserts were used. The rake and the clearance angle are respectively equal to 0° and 11°.

The experimental set-up is given in figure 6. The distance that separates the lens from the workpiece surface was adjusted to theoretically 23,8mm. Perpendicularity of the workpiece surface to the tool rake face was adjusted to (+0, +10 μ m).

Figure 6: experimental set-up for instrumented orthogonal cutting test.

2.5 Optical parameters

Fastcam APX-RS high-speed camera was used. The camera resolution was setting at 512x512 pixels leading to an observed scene size equal to 0,58x0,58mm². This size was validated by observing a 1mm graduated target with a resolution of 10 μ m/division. Therefore, the pixel size theoretically equal to 1,13 μ m was adopted for the displacement field conversion from pixel to micron unit.

The integration time was chosen in order to reduce blur that may occurs on the recorded image. Setting a maximum of 2,21 pixels displacement, the corresponding integration time is equal to 50 μ s. Optical system without coaxial illumination given in figure 11.a is used. It was mounted on 4-axis manual stage (T_x, T_y, T_z, R_z) required for adjustment. A 150W light source with optical fiber equipped with a focus system (Figure 4) is used for illumination. At the distance of 20mm, the spot size is equal to \varnothing 5,5mm.

Assuming that the speed of one segment chip formation is equal to the cutting speed and the segment width is equal to the feed (Pottier, 2014), the number of images per one segment chip function of frame rate can be predicted. Under the cutting condition given in table 4, 40 images per one segment chip can be obtained using a frame rate of 10000fps.

3 Kinematic fields measurement

3.1 DIC parameters

Digital Image Correlation was applied on 46 images captured during one segment chip formation. The DIC parameters using with Ncorr software (Blaber, 2015) are summarized in table 1.

A local approach with a Zero-Normalized Sum of Squared Differences (ZNSSD) correlation criteria was offered by the DIC software. This correlation criteria ensures no sensitivity to both offset and linear scale in lighting (Pan, 2009).

Table 1: DIC parameters.

Subset radius (pixels)	Subset spacing (pixels)	Strain radius
15	1	5

3.2 Displacement measurement uncertainties

The « Mean Intensity Gradient » (MIG) approach (Pan, 2010) was employed to predict the standard deviation of the displacement. Two consecutive images were captured before motion under the same optical parameters used during the cutting test. The standard deviation of the measured noise was found equal to 1,05. The MIG parameter is equal to 5,12/pixels². With a subset diameter of 30pixels, the obtained standard deviation of the displacement is equal to 0,0096 pixels \approx 0,011 μ m.

3.3 Results of kinematic fields measurement

Results of kinematic fields measurement are presented in figure 7 with an image increment of 10. Results of only 40 images, before the segment chip starts to slide with respect to the shear plan, are presented. Knowing the pixel size (1,13 μ m/pixel), the displacement field along x-axis (figure 7.a) and y-axis (figure 7.b) were obtained after conversion from pixel to micron unit. The components of the Euler-Almansi strain fields A_{xx} , A_{xy} and A_{yy} are presented respectively in figure 7.c, d and e leading to determine the equivalent strain field given in figure 7.f. Coherent results were found regarding the mechanisms of chip formation during orthogonal cutting tests. The segment chip was found to be subjected to compression along the x-axis according to the measured A_{xx} strain field. In parallel, shear strain (Figure 7.d) was increasing near the tool tip and reach a maximum value of 1 before it starts to propagate toward the free surface of the workpiece leading to high localized shear band. The subsurface of the workpiece below the machined surface is subjected to compression along the y-axis which is consistent due to the change of the material flow induced by the sharpness radius of the cutting tool. Moreover, the three components (A_{xx} , A_{xy} and A_{yy}) strain fields measured at the subsurface of the workpiece and far from the machined surface was equal to 0 which match with the assumption of rigid body motion in this zone.

An elastic springback of the material after the workpiece has passed through the clearance face of the cutting tool seems to occur according to the measured displacement fields along y-axis. The cutting tool edge can be centered with respect to the camera window in order to study the surface integrity of the machined surface.

Figure 7: displacement along a) x-axis ; and b) y-axis (in μm) ; Euler-Almansi strain field :c) A_{xx} ; d) A_{xy} and e) A_{yy} ; and f) equivalent strain field.

3.4 Accuracy assessment

For accuracy assessment of the results of the kinematic fields measurement, the correlation residue was examined and analysed from the following figure :

Figure 8: a) correlation residue map ; and b) occurrence of the correlation residue.

During the matching procedure between a given subset in the reference image and its correspondance in the deformed image, good match can be indicated when the correlation residue is close from 0. Figure 8.a gives the correlation residue in all the calculation nodes. Occurrence of the correlation residue (Figure 8.b) was fitted by a normal distribution for analysis. The mean values was found to be close from 0 with a maximum standard deviation of 0,132 which indicates property of the DIC application.

4 Conclusion

First orthogonal cutting test was conducted in order to validate the optical system. An acceptable image quality was obtained with sufficient spatial resolution ($1,13\mu\text{m}$) that leads to identify high localized deformation band during Ti-6Al-4V segment chip formation. Optical solution for focalised light beam can be recommended in the context of kinematic fields measurement during machining using optical system without coaxial illumination.

Coherent results of kinematic fields measurement were found. The measured strain fields correlate with the mechanisms of segment chip formation during orthogonal cutting test on titanium alloys. The evolution of the strain components (A_{xx} , A_{xy} and A_{yy}) indicate that the segment chip is mainly subjected to compression along x direction and shear along high localized shear band. Moreover, the correlation residue was found to be close from 0 in approximately all the calculation nodes which proves the property of the DIC application and therefore reliability of the measured kinematic fields.

In future work, sensitivity of the kinematic fields to both the subset size and out of-plane motion will be examined and orthogonal cutting tests will be conducted with the optical system reinforced by coaxial illumination. Influence of the cutting conditions on the measured kinematic fields in the primary shear zone will be studied. Moreover, the level of the strain fields reached in the tertiary shear zone can be studied function the tool sharpness radius. Post-mortem analysis can be made on collected chips in order to depict correlation with the measured kinematic fields and therefore the effect of the cutting process on the material microstructure.

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